

India's Act East Policy and China Factor

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ABSTRACT: The launch of India's Act East Policy and its visible foray into Southeast Asia has initiated a new great game in the region. There is a tussle between India and China to establish its influence in Myanmar in particular and Southeast Asia region in general. This is particularly because Myanmar is geo-strategically and geo-economically significant for rival nations of India and China. There is much to gain for both India and China by having a constructive engagement in Myanmar. India's early diplomatic dilemma vis-à-vis Myanmar owing to issue of democracy and the fact that China successfully managed to woo Myanmar since the early years makes it imperative for India to correct its diplomatic folly by having a meaningful engagement with Myanmar in present era given its ambitious Act East Policy.

KEYWORD: Act East Policy, China, Engagement, Myanmar, South East Asia.

INTRODUCTION:

The collision of geostrategic interests in Myanmar between India and China is often referred to as 'a new Great Game'. Myanmar as a country has the same significance for both India and China in both geo-political and geo-economic sense. Strategic and development considerations drive both India's and China's long-term vision of its relationship with Myanmar. Access to the Indian Ocean, stability in border areas, energy security, economic cooperation and maintaining friendly relations with other developing countries are the objectives that China aims to achieve by maintaining a cordial relationship with Myanmar. On the other hand strengthening relations with ASEAN countries, containing China's growing influence in the region, tackling insurgency problems in the North-East region and obtaining access to huge oil and gas reserve of Myanmar are India's objectives in Myanmar.

Myanmar is rich in energy resources which assume significance for both India and China who are keen to diversify their sources of energy as their economy expand. Yangon is also important for Beijing to stimulate the growth of the latter's landlocked western provinces which border Myanmar. Myanmar's trade with China is much greater than that with India. China has significant investments in Myanmar and plays a dominant role in oil and gas, hydropower and infrastructure sectors in Myanmar. China has great interest in the natural resources-rich Myanmar, which is evident from the range of its investments, from hydropower to mining to natural gas, with bidding competition from India. China, the biggest lender to Myanmar, and remains the biggest trading partner. Further, Beijing remained a faithful partner and supporter whenever Myanmar needed its support. The strong bilateral relationship was manifested at the

United Nation Security Council in January 2007 when China vetoed a draft resolution on Myanmar that demanded the release of all political prisoners, the initiation of a widespread political dialogue, and an end to military attacks and human right abuses against the ethnic minorities.ⁱ

For China all roads have led to Myanmar. The opening up of trade between Yunnan and Myanmar and the strengthening of ties more generally is seen in China as a strategic hedge against over-dependence on the straits of Malacca, as well as a way of developing a new outlet to the sea for its landlocked interior.ⁱⁱ Accelerated development of central and western China, especially the Yunnan province, is seen as contingent on breaking through the sub-region's landlocked situation by securing a permanent access to the Indian Ocean through Myanmar territory. This would give to China immense strategic and security advantages vis-à-vis India and other major rivals has been quite evident.ⁱⁱⁱ

Given China's success in building and maintaining an extensive network of road, rail, gas and oil pipelines connecting its southern border to Myanmar's south-western coast through a multipurpose north-south corridor running through Myanmar, it is but evident that it would greatly serve China in realizing its strategic and development goals in the country. China is clearly set to take major strides in promoting its triple interests: energy security, economic development and strategic advantage.^{iv}

There are several factors that drive the relationship between China and Myanmar. In the early years after the end of British colonialism in the region, proximity in the political and diplomatic domain has been the basis of the relationship between the two countries. In the military era, both side depicted their relation as a relationship between 'cousins'. Further, when Myanmar was internationally isolated, defence cooperation with China, which significantly continues even today, warmed up the relation to great heights. Myanmar's powerful military's need for arms and equipment, training and maintenance has been met by China. It is important to mention that the nature and extent of defence cooperation between the two countries is significantly greater than the rest of defence partners in the region.

China utilized the window of opportunity that came up in 1988 when Myanmar was internationally isolated for crushing the people's movement for democracy. Since then China has stepped up its influence through economic, military and development assistance. This has cushioned Myanmar against international sanctions by providing most of military hardware and build up its army in strength and quality. Majority of Myanmar's defence equipments are of Chinese origin. China has also taken full advantage of the distinct geographic, political and ethnic advantages it enjoys with Myanmar. Unlike ethnic Indian community, which had been languishing as second class citizens under Myanmar citizenship laws, China has managed the absorption of ethnic Chinese as citizens of Myanmar. China's strategic objective appears to be to gain direct access to Bay of Bengal and Andaman Sea through Myanmar bypassing the narrow Strait of Malacca. With this aim in view China had been underwriting the development roads from northern borders to south. China has proved time and again itself as a valuable ally internationally whenever efforts were made in the UN Security Council to discuss Myanmar.^v

Thus, strategic aspect of India's Act East Policy is more specifically revolves around China factor. Strategically China is the most critical factor for India to reckon with while venturing to attain its goals envisaged in its Look East Policy. India's Act East Policy of establishing closer link with South East Asia is viewed as an attempt to foreclose the region from becoming an exclusive sphere of Chinese influence. China has already showed its displeasure as regard of Southeast Asian countries' attempt to draw India into the region.^{vi} India's focus on Myanmar as a key neighbour on the eastern flank is driven by the reality of Myanmar being the country where China meets India.^{vii}

CONTAINING CHINA IN MYANMAR:

India's Look East Policy represents its effort to cultivate extensive economic and strategic relations with the nation of South East Asia in order to bolster its standing as a regional power and a counter weight to

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the strategic influence of the People's Republic of China.^{viii} Anything that promotes China's interests in its immediate neighborhood, or expands China's influence, worries India.^{ix} Economic requirement and the China "fixation" have guided India's policy towards East Asia.^x

Given the long history of India's China-centered Southeast Asia Policy throughout the Cold War period, it is natural that the two countries will not see eye to eye when entering each other's "area of influence". As India penetrates more into Chinese backyard in Southeast Asia in the new century, the confrontation between two Asian giants is inevitable. Also, given the lack of mutual trust in their relationship, the involvement of the Asian neighbours anywhere in the world is naturally seen as a competition between the two powers to shove out each other.^{xi}

The unpleasant relationship that India share with China in the aftermath of the 1962 War and the latter's support to the non-state armed groups from India's Northeast region have prompted India to keep a check on Chinese engagement with Myanmar. China's continuous engagement with Myanmar is of major concern for India, such as Coco Island (which was leased out to China) and in developing activities of the naval bases in Sittwe, Hianggyi, Khaukphyu, Mergui and Zadetkyikyan; also investment of one billion in the mining sector and involvement in logging and granting grants, concessional loans or debt relief among others. As China is gaining access to these strategic maritime locations and influence and control over Myanmar's rich resources and economy, it will put India in a grossly disadvantageous position.^{xii}

In view of growing Chinese influence in South East Asia, India has also pursued a policy of increasing engagement with the countries of Southeast Asia. India has stepped up engagement with South East Asia and East Asia fueled by its need for cooperation on counter-terrorism, humanitarian relief, anti-piracy, maritime and energy security, confidence-building and balancing the influence of other powers, notably China.^{xiii} India's moves to forge close relations with Myanmar are motivated by a desire to counter China's growing influence as a regional leader and enhance its own influence and standing. Concerns and tensions increased in India over China's extensive military involvement in developing ports, naval and intelligence facilities and industries, specifically the upgrading of a naval base in Sittwe, a major seaport located close to the eastern Indian city Kolkata.^{xiv}

It is evident that India is now intending to play a proactive role in her traditional balancing policy vis-a-vis China. This gets clear studying India's focus on bilateral relations with China-wary countries of Southeast Asia. India is forging bilateral strategic relations with the China-wary countries of East Asia. The China factor has unrelentingly worked in India's Southeast and later East Asia policy. Given her traditional "contain China" objective in Southeast Asia, India wants to play a vital role in the fast emerging geostrategic ambience of the region where the regional players also pursue the same policy of India vis-a-vis China.^{xv} India's grand strategy is to emerge as a major player in order to contain the Chinese influence by associating with those countries which has potential to rein in Chinese influence in the region.^{xvi}

Myanmar's strategic importance and growing Chinese influence with the junta regime has over the years, compelled India in forging closer ties with Nay Pyi Daw. In the early 1990s, faced with changes in the international order, India felt the compelling need to reignite its relation with Myanmar. India, "based on its need to build a close bilateral relation with Myanmar, renewed its policy and moved towards 'constructive engagement' with the military regime".^{xvii} India's focus on Myanmar as a key component in its Act East Policy is driven by the reality of Myanmar being the country where China meets India. One of the important aspects of India's reinvented Act East Policy is to contain China's growing influence in South East Asia and Myanmar in particular.

To contain and counter China, India has developed multilateral organizations such as the Mekong Ganga Cooperation and BIMSTEC, forging extensive cooperation on environmental, economic development, security and strategic affairs, permitting the growth of influence beyond South Asia and without the tense

and obstructive presence of Pakistan and China that has stalled its efforts in the South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC). India became a sectoral dialogue partner with ASEAN in 1992, in 1995 was given an advisory status, a member of the Council for Security Cooperation in the Asia-Pacific, a member of the ASEAN Regional Forum in 1996, and a summit level partner (on par with China, Japan and South Korea) in 2002. India also acceded to ASEAN'S Treaty of Amity and Cooperation in Southeast Asia in 2003. In many cases, India's membership to these forums has been a result of attempts by the region to balance China's growing influence in the area. Notably, Japan brought India into ASEAN+6 to dilute the ASEAN+3 process, where China is dominant, while Singapore and Indonesia played a significant role in bringing India into the East Asia Summit. The United States and Japan have also lobbied for India's membership in the Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC).^{xviii}

A sense of rivalry felt by India towards China and its successful push for closer economic ties with South-East Asia initially figured prominently in India's push towards ASEAN. India felt forced to counter China's push into the rest of Asia with moves of its own. BIMSTEC and the Mekong-Ganga Cooperation, for instance, are regional cooperation agreements initiated by India directed towards countering China's growing influence in the region.^{xix} Competition with China strongly influenced India's BIMSTEC initiative. It was designed to partly counter the proposed 1997 Bangladesh, China, India and Burma initiative. The Mekong-Ganga Cooperation was another India initiative, announced in 2000 and designed to partly counter the Greater Mekong Sub region growth area which also involves China. With members including India, Cambodia, Laos, Burma, Vietnam and Thailand, the Mekong-Ganga Cooperation has all of the Greater Mekong Sub region members except China.^{xx}

Over the years, India's Act East Policy has able to strengthen India's political, economic and cultural relations with the Southeast Asian countries and the Pacific and has ensured that India place itself as an important part of the emerging economic and security architecture of the region. Commerce with Southeast Asia and East Asia accounts for 45% of India's foreign trade. Trade and Commerce between India and Myanmar have been growing rapidly in recent years. India is today Myanmar's 4th largest trading partner after Thailand, China and Singapore. India is also the second largest export market after Thailand, absorbing 25 percent of Myanmar's total exports and is the 7th most important source of country's imports. As a result of growing Chinese influence in Myanmar as well as the safe haven of insurgent groups of North-East India, drugs and arms trafficking occurring along the Indo-Burmese border, India, in recent years, has sought to shore up ties with the military junta. Numerous economic arrangements have been established apart from developing road connectivity between the two countries.

India's growing economic cooperation with Myanmar has led India to explore Myanmar's rich oil and gas reserves. The Oil and Natural Gas Corporation (ONGC) and Gas Authority of India Limited (GAIL), have been involved in the Shwe gas field with 20 percent and 10m percent stakes, respectively, in A-1 and A-3 offshore blocks, which have combined reserves of 4.53 TCF. Essar Oil Ltd is the first Indian private sector company to have signed two Production Sharing Contracts (PSCs) with Myanmar for oil exploration in two blocks- one offshore (Block A-2) and the other onshore (Block L) in May 2005. On 24 September, 2007 the ONGC's subsidiary ONGC Videsh, signed a deal with Myanmar Oil and Gas Enterprise (MOGE) to explore for gas in three more offshore blocks.^{xxi}

In the field of military cooperation, India is slowly becoming a regular supplier of arms to Myanmar, joining the ranks of China, Russia and Ukraine. Initially India had supplied low tech arms and armaments, including 105 mm guns, T-55 tanks, light helicopters, transport planes, artillery ammunitions and some naval craft. However, there had been a progressive up gradation of these exports which includes counterinsurgency helicopters, avionics upgrades for Myanmar air force's Russian and Chinese made fighter planes, and naval surveillance aircraft.^{xxii} While China enjoys a growing dominance in Myanmar's economy, some astute thinking by India could make it a serious competitor. To do that, though, New

Delhi needs to be more assertive and aggressive in projecting its own strengths. It should make special efforts to highlight its shared history and institutional advantages, and its belief in partnership rather than creating appendages. This is important, because the ever increasing Chinese economic presence is slowly but surely causing resentment amongst sections of the Myanmar populace.^{xxiii}

One of the sensitive issues in India's Act East Policy is the security cooperation with neighbouring countries. New Delhi thinks that Mandalay is close to China and the Chinese wind can reach the Northeast from Mandalay itself. Further, stability and security of the strategic Northeast region of India is of prime importance. Therefore, in spite of regular engagement, the 'China factor' continues to cast a dark shadow on India's connectivity projects which largely cast apprehension over India's ambitious Act East Policy. With time it has becoming more practical for India to understand that as New Delhi cannot stop China building connectivity projects, the solution lies in "pro-active participation" in the process.

Regardless of whether Myanmar completes its democratic transition or retreats to resume its previous pariah status, its geostrategic significance and natural resources will continue to shape the balance of power in a region where Chinese and Indian interests intersect.^{xxiv} On the other hand, given the fact that it took India many decades to reach present state of cordial relation with Myanmar and given the underlying and far reaching objectives in the relation between two neighbours, India cannot afford to not act in a manner that displeases the one in power, whether a popular government or a government run by generals. India, in any circumstance will not compromise its relation with Myanmar knowing the fact that it is where both India and China meet for a new great game.

CONCLUSION:

Given the geo-strategic and geo-economic importance of Myanmar in South Asia, Southeast Asia and East Asia, it occupies a center stage in the tussle for influence between India and China. Neither India nor China can afford to lose out on Myanmar. India's action plan should be to match with China in attaining the level of engagement that China shares today with Myanmar in all fronts. Correcting the early foreign policy blunder vis-à-vis Myanmar, India, driving by pragmatism has to let its idealism in back seat and let the long term strategic and economic goal take the front seat keeping China in its mind.

1. Nehginpao Kipgen, Myanmar: A Political History, Oxford University Press, New Delhi, 2016, pp-181-182
2. Myint-U, Thant, *Burma and the New Crossroads of Asia: Where China Meets India*, Faber and Faber Limited, London, 2011,p-9
3. Rajiv Bhatia, India-Myanmar Relations: Changing Contours, Routledge, New York, 2018, p-197.
4. Ibid, p-197.
5. R.Hariharan, Coming to terms with Myanmar, Dialogue, Vol. 9 No. 1, July-September, 2007, p-73.
6. Omprasad Gadde and Gupta, Kumar Amit, ed. *India's Act East Policy Through Northeast: Opportunities and Challenges*, Mittal Publications, New Delhi, 2017,p-22.
7. India-Myanmar Relation: Looking from the Border, Conference Report, 28-29 September 2015, Burma Centre Delhi, New Delhi.
8. Omprasad Gadde and Gupta, Kumar Amit,p-21
9. Nehginpao Kipgen, Myanmar: A Political Hstory, Oxford University Press, New Delhi, 2016, p-178
10. Subhadeep Bhattacharya, Looking East Since 1947: India's Southeast Asia Policy, KW Publishers Pvt Ltd, New Delhi, 2016, p-137.

11. Ibid, p-135
12. Pankaj Jha & Rahul Mishra,ed. *Integrating North East In India's Act Est Policy*, Indian Council of World Affairs, New Delhi p-74.
13. Kamal Jhadav, *India-Myanmar Relations*, Gaurav Book Centre Pvt. Ltd, New Delhi, 2019, p-132.
14. Ibid, pp-11-12
15. Subhadeep Bhattacharya, *Looking East Since 1947: India's Southeast Asia Policy*, KW Publishers Pvt Ltd, New Delhi, 2016, p-148
16. Ibid, p-154
17. K. Kokho, 'Indo-Myanmar Economic Relations: An Overview of the Evolving Dynamics', eds. Pankaj Jha, & Rahul Mishra, *Integrating North East In India's Act East Policy*, Indian Council of World Affairs, New Delhi, 2017, p.78.
18. Kamal Jhadav, *India-Myanmar Relations*, Gaurav Book Centre Pvt. Ltd, New Delhi,2019, p-133
19. Devojit Phukan ed., *Look East Policy and North East India*, SSDN Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi, 2013, p-84.
20. Ibid, p-89
21. Kamal Jhadav, pp-177-78
22. R.Hariharan, *Coming to terms with Myanmar*, Dialogue, Vol. 9 No. 1, July-September, 2007, p-79
23. Baladas Ghoshal, *A Critical Evaluation of India's Engagement with Myanmar*, Conference Report on Look East Policy India and Myanmar Pitching for Greater Connectivity, Burma Centre Delhi, 4 August 2014, New Delhi, p-24.
24. Ibid, p-27